

Guiding Questions: Expanded Set Across the Five Analytical Dimensions (D1–D5)

A Decision Framework for Selecting Technology Acceptance and Use Models: TAM, TAM2, TAM3, UTAUT, and UTAUT2

Anonymized for peer review

This document presents the expanded set of 16 guiding inquiries that operationalize the five analytical dimensions (D1–D5) of the proposed framework. The dimensions generally follow a three-tier architecture composed of primary classification, refinement, and disambiguation. Dimension D4 includes an additional internal tie-breaking inquiry (D4.4), because explanatory focus may require resolving tensions among determinant type, social influence, and affective, hedonic, or habit-related elements.

The inquiries were derived from the structural comparison of TAM, TAM2, TAM3, UTAUT, and UTAUT2, grounded in the foundational articles (Davis, 1989; Venkatesh & Davis, 2000; Venkatesh & Bala, 2008; Venkatesh et al., 2003; Venkatesh, Thong & Xu, 2012) and informed by critical reviews (Turner et al., 2010; Williams et al., 2015; De Brito & Ramos, 2019; Malatji et al., 2020; Batista et al., 2023). Conditional inquiries (third tier) apply only when the primary classification yields an ambiguous or mixed result. All conditional inquiries include the methodological convention of a "no clear predominance" alternative.

These inquiries constitute Component 2 of the framework and are intended to guide the researcher in positioning their study across the five dimensions before consulting the descriptive profiles (Component 3).

D1: Application Context

D1.1: Primary classification of context

In which predominant setting will the investigated technology be used?

- (a) Organizational, with use associated with tasks, routines, or institutional responsibilities.
- (b) Individual consumer context, with use associated with personal choices of the user.
- (c) Hybrid, with analytically relevant elements of both contexts.

D1.2: Role of the user under analysis

What is the user's position in relation to the organization responsible for the technology?

- (a) The user is a member of the organization, such as an employee, internal collaborator, or institutional agent.

- (b) The user is external to the organization, such as a client, citizen, patient, or consumer.
- (c) The user uses the technology in a predominantly autonomous manner, without institutional ties relevant to the use under analysis.

D1.3: Coherence verification in hybrid cases

If D1.1 was classified as hybrid, which context best represents the predominant motivation for use?

- (a) Institutional motivations predominate, such as performance, task fulfillment, or organizational requirements.
- (b) Personal motivations predominate, such as individually perceived usefulness, convenience, satisfaction, or user experience.
- (c) There is no clear predominance between institutional and personal motivations.

D2: Intended Type of Use

D2.1: Primary classification of the use regime

What is the use regime presupposed by the context under investigation?

- (a) Voluntary, when adoption and use of the technology depend predominantly on the user's choice.
- (b) Mandatory, when there is formal or institutional imposition for the use of the technology.
- (c) Mixed, when elements of voluntariness and mandatoriness coexist in an analytically relevant manner.

D2.2: Interpretive refinement of voluntariness

Considering the reality of the user under study, which aspect of voluntariness is most relevant to the research?

- (a) Formal voluntariness, defined by institutional rules or explicit conditions of use.
- (b) Perceived voluntariness, related to the user's subjective perception of their freedom of choice.
- (c) The investigation jointly considers formal and perceived voluntariness.

D2.3: Resolution of ambiguity in mixed regimes

If D2.1 was classified as mixed, which element exerts greater influence on the use of the technology?

- (a) Elements of mandatoriness predominate, such as norms, requirements, or institutional consequences.
- (b) Elements of voluntariness predominate, such as user choice, personal motivations, or perceived convenience.
- (c) There is no clear predominance between the two elements.

D3: Adoption Stage

D3.1: Primary classification of the adoption stage

Which stage of the adoption process does the research predominantly investigate?

- (a) Initial acceptance, focused on the formation of behavioral intention and the initial decision to adopt the technology.
- (b) Continued use, focused on use behavior after initial adoption of the technology.
- (c) Multiple stages, when initial acceptance and continued use are both central to the analytical objectives of the research.

D3.2: Refinement of the analytical focus

Considering the stage under investigation, which analytical variable is of greatest interest to the research?

- (a) Behavioral intention, as the primary variable to be explained.
- (b) Use behavior, as the primary variable to be explained.
- (c) The investigation jointly considers behavioral intention and use behavior.

D3.3: Resolution of ambiguity in multi-stage studies

If D3.1 was classified as multiple stages, which stage carries greater weight in the declared objectives of the research?

- (a) Interest in initial acceptance and in the factors that precede use predominates.
- (b) Interest in continued use and in the factors that sustain this behavior over time predominates.
- (c) There is no clear predominance between initial acceptance and continued use.

D4: Explanatory Focus

D4.1: Predominant nature of the determinant

What type of determinant does the study prioritize to explain technology acceptance or use?

- (a) Predominantly cognitive-instrumental, focused on beliefs about usefulness and effort associated with use.
- (b) Cognitive-instrumental extended by social, contextual, or experience-related factors.
- (c) Multiple types of determinants, including cognitive, social, contextual, and affective factors, articulated in an integrated structure.

D4.2: Relevance of social influence

What is the role of social influence in the proposed investigation?

- (a) Social influence is not central to the objectives of the research.
- (b) Social influence is relevant and needs to be captured, especially in its normative forms or those associated with recognition and status.
- (c) Social influence is relevant in a broader formulation, as expectations regarding technology use by relevant others.

D4.3: Relevance of affective, hedonic, or habit-related elements

Does the study require sensitivity to affective, hedonic, or behavioral elements of a non-strictly instrumental nature?

- (a) No, the focus falls predominantly on instrumental determinants, without requiring special sensitivity to these elements.
- (b) Yes, especially affective or emotional aspects related to the use experience, such as enjoyment, anxiety, or discomfort.
- (c) Yes, especially hedonic motivation, habit, or price value in consumer contexts.

D4.4: Internal tie-breaking rule

If the responses to D4.1, D4.2, and D4.3 point to different models, which aspect carries the greatest weight in the explanatory objectives of the research?

- (a) The predominant nature of the determinants, as per D4.1.
- (b) The role of social influence, as per D4.2.
- (c) The incorporation of affective, hedonic, or habit-related elements, as per D4.3.
- (d) There is no clear predominance among the three aspects.

D5: Intended Analytical Granularity

D5.1: Primary classification of intended granularity

What level of analytical granularity does the study intend to achieve in explaining the phenomenon?

- (a) Low granularity, with a lean explanatory structure focused on core determinants.
- (b) Intermediate granularity, with a controlled expansion of the explanatory structure to capture additional relevant determinants.
- (c) High granularity, with a detailed explanatory structure to incorporate multiple antecedents, moderators, and relationships among constructs.

D5.2: Balance between conceptual parsimony and explanatory coverage

Considering the intended granularity, which orientation best characterizes the analytical design of the research?

- (a) Prioritizes conceptual parsimony, favoring economy and interpretive clarity.
- (b) Prioritizes explanatory coverage, favoring breadth and detail of determinants.
- (c) Seeks a balance between conceptual parsimony and explanatory coverage, according to the demands of the study.

D5.3: Resolution of ambiguity between parsimony and coverage

If D5.2 was classified as balance, which orientation prevails when there is tension between conceptual parsimony and explanatory coverage?

- (a) Conceptual parsimony prevails, favoring leaner models even if some aspects remain unaddressed.
- (b) Explanatory coverage prevails, favoring denser models even at the cost of greater complexity.
- (c) There is no clear predominance between conceptual parsimony and explanatory coverage.